

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

FORMATION OF NATIONAL PATRIOTIC CONSCIOUSNESS IN THE CONDITIONS OF FULL-SCALE WAR AS A FACTOR OF THE UNITY OF UKRAINIAN SOCIETY

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Abstract

The article analyzes the process of formation and development of national-patriotic education in Ukraine and its role in consolidation of Ukrainian society in terms of a full-scale Russian-Ukrainian War. The following general scientific methods were used during the studies: analysis, synthesis, deduction, induction and generalization. There can be also highlighted the principles and following aspects of patriotic education: social, educational, protective and cultural. Modern Ukrainian society needs consolidation, in particular through the national-patriotic education, as it has not yet encountered such a threat to national security and sovereignty as is currently represented by armed Russian aggression. The authors substantiate the need for such education and provide certain recommendations regarding its effective development. The practical significance of the received scientific results is that they can be used for the development of educational initiatives and civil development programs by authorized institutions in order to raise the level of national consciousness of society.

Keywords: National-Patriotic Education, Ukrainian Society, Youth, Unity of Ukrainians, Young Generation, Volunteering.

Introduction

For a long time, Russia (hereinafter referred to as the Russian Federation) continues a hybrid War against Ukraine, using various tools and means of influence, including information propaganda and Information & Psychological Operations (IPsO), which are aimed at Ukrainian society, especially the young generation. For a long time, the state did not actively protect the national ideas and values of citizens, and did not pay enough attention to national-patriotic education. However, after the beginning of the Russian-Ukrainian War in 2014, the rapid development of that area has started with the efforts of citizens and activists. There was an intensification of national-patriotic movements and organizations aimed at supporting Ukrainian national identity, such as volunteer battalions and public associations that assist the army and local communities in the affected territories. Among children's and youth organizations, it was "Kozachata" [5], "Plast" [28], "Union of Ukrainian Youth" [38]. The "Phoenix Wings" should be noted among volunteer organizations [35], "The People's Project" [27], "Come Back Alive" Foundation [6]. The popularity of patriotic media projects that oppose Russian propaganda and disseminate objective information about events in Ukraine has also increased. However, the insufficient level of attention to national-patriotic education can undermine society's ability to effectively confront Russian aggression. Today, it is important not only to continue the national-patriotic movement, but also to involve broader population, in particular ordinary citizens, therein. Awareness of self-identity and common values will contribute to the effective consolidation of society and resistance

to hostile influences, which will allow creating a single information front line in the defence of national interests during the War.

As emphasized in the Decree of the President of Ukraine dated December 1, 2016 No. 534/2016, "patriotic and spiritual education of the younger generation will ensure the integrity of the people of Ukraine, its national revival, unification of different ethnic groups and regions of the country, socio-economic and democratic development of Ukraine..." [10].

The relevance of the study lies in the need to investigate modern national-patriotic education in Ukraine in detail for its development and wider spread, in particular through state and civil initiatives.

Review of sources and literature

Certain aspects of national-patriotic education have already been covered in a number of works of domestic scientists. In particular, I.D. Bekh, L.V. Kaniševska and R.V. Malynoshevskiyi consider the priorities of military-patriotic education of children and youth in terms of the Russian-Ukrainian War and after it, developed by the Institute of Educational Problems of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine, covering institutional, infrastructural, socio-cultural and educational aspects, as well as methodical approaches and principles of modern military-patriotic education, such as de-Russification, national orientation, educational process humanization, consolidation etc [2]. O. Haziova, L. Sorochuk and A. Kononenko, analyzing the practical experience of teachers of the introduction of Ukrainian studies into the system of national-patriotic education, emphasize the growing interest of many Ukrainians in the history of Ukraine, the

Ukrainian language, literature, and cultural heritage at the current stage. Therefore, the extremely responsible mission of teachers today is to educate the future political elite who will be ready to defend the importance of the Ukrainian language, history and culture, thereby affirming their national identity [15]. N. Bondarenko in his article emphasizes national identity as a key tool for countering the Kremlin's influence, considers the ideas of Ukrainian intellectuals and the possibility of using them to improve the system of national-patriotic education [4]. The studies of O.V. Skrypniuk and Y.F. Zhovnirchuk describe theoretical and practical aspects of the state policy of Ukraine for patriotic education of youth, taking into account the current state and development prospects, a theoretical analysis of the concepts of "patriotism" and "education" was carried out [33]. The monograph of O. Rafalskyi, Ya. Kalakura, O. Kalakura and M. Yurii is interpreted the Ukrainian civilizational identity, attention is focused on the importance of a deep understanding of the historical, philosophical, sociological and cultural aspects of that concept in all its complexity and diversity. This makes it possible not only to consider the historical roots of the civilizational identity of Ukrainians, but also to understand its current state and significance for Ukrainian society, areas in which the popularization of that concept will make it possible to influence patriotic education positively [30].

We also used the Laws of Ukraine [19; 20]; strategies in the security field, approved by the relevant decrees of the President [22; 11]; statistical data of the National Security and Defence Magazine [44]. The analysis of those materials made it possible to obtain a comprehensive vision of Ukrainian national-patriotic education in terms of full-scale armed aggression of the Russian Federation.

A lot of studies conducted in the field of national-patriotic education do not take into account the aspects of gender equality, the possibility of using innovations in the educational process, as well as the development of tolerance and a culture of dialogue. However, the most urgent problem that remains outside the attention of research fellows is the actual implementation of the main goal of patriotic education, that is, the consolidation of Ukrainians as a single nation. Therefore, the main goal of that study is to determine the role of national-patriotic education in the process of uniting Ukrainian society in terms of full-scale aggression of the Russian Federation.

The modern Russian-Ukrainian genocidal war caused an increase in the unity of Ukrainian society, which was a consequence of the appearance of an external common enemy and the need to confront the same. The uniting is manifested in the consolidation of efforts to fight the enemy, faith in the Armed Forces of Ukraine, negative emotions towards the Russian Federation. This commonality of goals and views strengthened the tendency to consolidate representatives of various social groups and reduce differences in their political views and values. At now Ukrainians are going through many common experiences, which creates a common context of life for people regardless of their

place of residence, forms a common historical memory, contributes to the occurrence of a sense of unity.

Today, a number of summarizing works on the life of society, collisions of its development and future have been published. The works of V. Andrushchenko [1] consider the general problems of organization and social self-organization during the period of transformations in Ukraine at the end of the 20th and the beginning of the 21st centuries. O. Rafalskyi [29] characterized the socio-political processes in Ukraine in terms of the Russian-Ukrainian War and assessed the consolidation potential of the image of the future of Ukraine, and the scientists of the Center of Ukrainian Studies of T. Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, researching the consolidation of Ukrainianness in the post-colonial era, notes that the research material, which is largely relevant to our present day, "constantly undergoes variations and is filled with new phenomena and senses" [8]. The collective monograph of the scientists of the Institute of Sociology of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine [37] considers the global and local aspects of the war, the transformation of the institutional and social-group structure, shifts in the attitudes, expectations, value orientations of citizens, and the socio-psychological state of the population. V. Kryshchenko's articles highlight Moscow's aggressive policy towards Ukraine, which can be qualified as a policy of genocide, consider the problems of the consolidation of Ukrainian society, in particular the dividing lines in Ukrainian society that affect its ability to self-organize and develop [39; 40, 41]. T. Tsybmal emphasizes that consolidation under crisis conditions should be greater than in normal ones, and it also implies unity with other countries that support the common civilizational vector of our country's development. The author claims that, taking into account the crisis state of Ukrainian society, the conditions of the "hybrid" war, Ukraine today needs to strengthen social consolidation, the level of which has decreased slightly [36]. Foreign scientists L. Dion, J. Craige, E. Gellner analyze "full-scale" nations as a guarantee of social harmony. T. Gran, N. Darchevska, E. Wilson trace the peculiarities of Russia's modern expansionist policy, in particular its influence on Ukraine [43]. The use of the world experience of the study of the consolidation of society is complicated by the peculiarity of the genocidal war of the Russian Federation against Ukraine, its security threats in view of the possession of a huge arsenal of nuclear weapons by the Russian Federation.

Materials and methods

There were used the following methods to conduct studies: analysis, synthesis, comparison, interview, deduction, induction and generalization. The method of analysis was used for a detailed review and critical thinking of scientific and statistical data related to patriotic education in terms of war. Its application not only made it possible to consider the information received, but also to find out the interaction between various aspects of the above education and the events taking place in Ukraine. The analysis was effective in identifying the key factors influencing patriotic education in terms of war, and contributed to highlighting the main trends in that area. That approach made it possible to get a more

detailed understanding of the role of patriotism in consolidation of society and preservation of the identity of the Ukrainian nation during the conflict. At the same time, the synthesis in the study was applicable for combining and systematizing various information and aspects of patriotic education. Also, by synthesis, different approaches to patriotic education were taken into account, which made it possible to understand how certain aspects of patriotic education interact with each other and influence the formation of national consciousness and readiness to defend the state. The comparison was used to study statistical data related to sociological surveys for different years. Based on that method, there were created the appropriate tables that visualized the differences found between various parameters.

The interview method was used to collect empirical information on patriotic education. This method made it possible to obtain data on the attitude of ordinary citizens to certain aspects in that area. There were conducted the interviews with random citizens of different ages and genders, with their verbal consent, on city streets, in parks, and shopping malls. A total of 750 interviews were conducted during the month. In order to ensure representativeness, there were chosen the citizens for interviews: male (350) and female (400), from three age groups: youth (14–35 years old, 350 people), adults (35–60 years old, 300 people), people elderly (from 60 years old, 100 people). In turn, there was used the deduction to derive general principles and regularities of national-patriotic education from specific observations and analysis of facts obtained during the study. Further, the use of deduction made it possible to consider in more detail the logical connections between various aspects of national-patriotic education and its influence on consolidation of the civil society and formation of a patriot's personality. Induction was used to formulate hypotheses and make assumptions about possible cause-and-effect relationships in patriotic education during the armed conflict, as a factor capable of uniting Ukrainian society. Further, this method made it possible to identify new areas for studies in the field of patriotic education. Generalization was used to formulate general conclusions and recommendations based on the obtained study results. The application of generalization made it possible to systematize and combine the obtained data, highlight their meaning and impact on processes in society. By way of generalization, there were also summarized the key results and conclusions that were made during the study, on the basis of which recommendations were formulated for the improvement of patriotic education in order to increase the effectiveness of that process in modern conditions.

Basic material presentation

The present period of existence of independent Ukraine is one of the most difficult in its recent history, due to various political, economic and social challenges caused by the full-scale armed aggression of the Russian Federation. The war aimed at the occupation or destruction of Ukraine and intensive propaganda became a serious test for Ukrainian society, violating territorial integrity and national identity. Within such a situation, patriotic education of youth is recognized as key for the

development of the country and its national security.

Patriotism is an important component of national and social development and means that a person feels respect and love for the state in which he/she was born or lives. Patriotism contributes to the formation of public unity, unites society and encourages people to support and build state institutions, performance of civic duty. Patriotic feelings can arise from a variety of factors, such as history, culture, language, traditions and shared values, the importance of protecting freedom, democracy and human rights within the country. Patriotism has the potential to unite different social and cultural groups around common goals and ideals, which contributes to the maintenance of social unity and the development of the country [26]. At the same time, national patriotism or nationalism is a complex ideology and socio-political movement defined by the shared desire of a community's members, often sharing common features such as culture, history, language or ethnic origin, to create or maintain their/our own nation-state. It includes a wide range of feelings, from the maintenance of national identity and cultural heritage to the desire for political autonomy and sovereignty. Nationalism can arise as a reaction to historical events, external pressures, or perceived threats to a group's identity or autonomy. It often manifests itself in a sense of solidarity among the members of the nation, which pushes them to preserve and develop their unique identity, traditions and interests [23].

State policy in the field of national-patriotic education is an important factor that determines the quality and success of that process, and from the state of which the development of national self-awareness of the youth, their readiness to defend the state occurs. The patriotism of Ukrainians is one of the components necessary to achieve self-sufficiency and independence of the state in the world, and in present circumstances of a full-scale war between Ukraine and the Russian Federation, the state's policy in the field of education of youth as patriots turns out to be paramount in matters of national security.

Further, due to the terrorist attacks of the Russian Federation aimed at the civilian population, the creation of conditions for the occurrence of environmental and man-made disasters, as well as the mass mining of the temporarily occupied territories of Ukraine, an important task is to educate the young generation in the necessary safety habits. This includes developing effective behavioral patterns while in combat zones, studying the course of actions in case of emergency situations and increased information about mine danger in the de-occupied territories. Paying attention to the terrorist nature of the enemy's actions makes it obvious the need to systematically educate citizens to take responsibility for their own safety and the safety of others [2, p. 3]. However, in addition to the development of security skills, national-patriotic education is aimed at promoting self-awareness and self-identification of Ukrainians, forming a positive world perception, establishing a patriotic worldview. The key aspects of patriotic education are a full and comprehensive understanding of personal civic duty, confidence in actions aimed at the protection and development of Ukraine.

An essential part of national-patriotic education is the development of interest in the history of the Ukrainian people and the military traditions of the Armed Forces of Ukraine. The task of such education includes the formation of a responsible public position and conscious social activity of Ukrainians. The development and implementation of national-patriotic education involves not only the development of patriotic values, but also the creation of self-improvement conditions and the formation of a personality as a patriot [4, p. 4].

Goal, tasks and areas of national-patriotic education at the present stage

According to scientists from the I.F. Kuras Institute of Political and Ethnonational Studies of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, the process of forming national, civil, religious and civilizational identity takes place throughout the life of an individual. This process begins with upbringing in the family and receiving general education, which is the main component of the continuous education system. Its main areas include civic, political and cultural socialization, the formation of a scientific outlook, democratic and legal culture, as well as active participation in public life, which contributes to the development of both the individual and society [30]. Involvement in this process of patriotic education makes it possible to bypass negative social phenomena, increase the general historical and cultural awareness of Ukrainians and the level of their consolidation. It is important to emphasize that patriotism, as a complex of feelings, is highlighted through intellectual, emotional and volitional components. An individual's sense of value in relation to a specific concept, person or phenomenon pushes him/her to act, forming motivation. Patriotism combines an emotional, effective and valuable attitude to various aspects of life, such as the state, nature, nation, national history, as well as material and spiritual achievements of society. In turn, the modern process of socialization, which is studied by social pedagogy, has a characteristic feature – its transformational nature in terms of a change in the social context. Situations that seemed typical for certain conditions can suddenly vary in the perception of citizens, especially in the situation in which Ukrainian society is now. This is especially appearing in the context of patriotism, which is an important aspect of socialization and interaction of the individual with society. Patriotism as a component of political culture affects an individual's attitude to the history, traditions and worldview of his/her country, forming his/her political identity. The structure of patriotic standards to be formed in the process of socialization determines the orientation of the individual in the "friend of foe" social system. These mechanisms can also influence the formation of attitudes towards large social groups, ethnic groups, foreign countries and other aspects at the macro level. A high level of patriotism determines an individual's political attitude towards the main political institutions of the state, the management system and personal active participation in political life. Moreover, patriotism actively mobilizes individuals, social groups and society as a whole to form political beliefs that cover various aspects of social life. The important influence of patriotism is also manifested in the formation

of political stereotypes that determine the specifics of society. As patriotism is an important factor in socialization, it influences the behavioral patterns of individuals, thus having a significant potential to promote effective socialization of children and youth, especially within the context of youth and education policy.

The goal of national-patriotic education is as follows: deepening national self-identification and awareness of the Ukrainian people as an independent and equal European nation; supporting love for the Ukrainian language, history, traditions and culture; transfer of knowledge and values by way of personal experience and active cooperation between generations through educational projects, cultural events and family discussions; formation of a citizen-patriot of Ukraine, capable not only of protecting, but also actively contributing to the development of the country as an independent and democratic state; increasing awareness of the constitutional rights and duties of citizens, using available educational and informational resources; contribute to the unification of the Ukrainian people, promoting dialogue and mutual understanding between different social groups and regions of the country, in particular through the development of intercultural and interregional cooperation. The implementation of this goal takes place by way of introduction of appropriate measures aimed at strengthening the national-patriotic consciousness of children and youth, commemorating the heroes of the struggle of the Ukrainian people for independence and territorial integrity, popularizing the national spiritual and cultural heritage and strengthening the unity and consolidation of Ukrainian society.

Among them: conversations, hours of remembrance, round tables, meetings of children and youth with participants in the Russian-Ukrainian War, volunteers, exhibitions in educational, cultural institutions, cultural information and educational projects aimed at popularizing the historical past of the Ukrainian people, preserving national cultural artistic traditions of Ukrainians, overcoming stereotypes and propagandist myths aimed at destroying the unity of the Ukrainian people, as well as holding competitions for school and student works on the issue of heroism of Ukrainian soldiers, displaying courage and bravery by them.

Therefore, the ideas of protection and love for the state, as well as preservation and nurturing of national memory and culture are recognized as key components of patriotic education. Consolidation of such ideas in society not only contributes to the formation of national consciousness, but also provides a strong foundation for the development of a civic position and active participation of citizens in the life of the country.

It should be noted that national-patriotic education is based on the following principles: national orientation, heredity of ideas, self-activity and self-regulation, social responsibility, historical and social memory, multiculturalism, humanization. The principle of national orientation is determined by the education of love for the state and the formation of national self-awareness. The principle of self-activity and self-regulation contributes to the development of the civic position of the individual and its ability to critical thinking and

self-evaluation. The principle of multiculturalism provides for the integration of Ukrainian culture among European ones. The principle of social responsibility consists in the correspondence between the national-patriotic education and real social challenges and the readiness to stand up for the defence of the state. The principle of historical and social memory provides for the preservation of cultural and historical heritage of the Ukrainian people. The principle of heredity of ideas is aimed at preserving samples of Ukrainian culture for future generations. The principle of humanization pays attention to the individual as the highest value.

The role of national-patriotic education is that it can be used as a means of supporting the Ukrainian state and the national movement, as well as forming ideas about Ukrainian nationality. By carrying out reforms in the field of education, there are taken measures to cultivate the Ukrainian identity, which also manifests itself in the strengthening of the state's defence capabilities. By promoting a sense of unity among the population, initiatives in the field of patriotic education contribute to ensuring national security. In effect, the education sector is becoming an extension of security efforts, developing curriculums to address national security issues and raising citizen awareness of national, local and individual security among the younger generation [13; p. 107].

The education system, as well as the activities of sports and patriotic clubs, have a great influence on the solution of tasks set before national-patriotic education in the state. In general terms, the educational institutions, implementing patriotic education, play a key role in the formation of patriotism and familiarization of the young generation with the political and national values of the state. Through specially developed curriculums, educational institutions aim to educate talented individuals who feel a deep emotional attachment to the state

where they were born or live. This goal is aimed not only at reducing ideological polarization between different racial and national groups, but also at socializing young people to accept the generally accepted values of society. By instilling patriotism, educational institutions contribute to the strengthening of social unity and counteract global anti-national influences [45, pp. 23–26].

The military-patriotic education of pupils, students and cadets is also particularly important, which is a necessary component of national-patriotic education. Such education is aimed at encouraging young people to preserve the security of Ukraine and the formation of moral qualities necessary for the defence of the state, encouraging them to choose a military career. As a general rule, the younger generation is involved in military-patriotic education. It should be noted that military-patriotic education is definitely part of the country's national security system and is a key element of the new generation humanitarian education. This is an important component aimed at the formation of patriotic feelings in them, as well as the maintenance of physical and moral health, the development of educational, physical, psychological, social and moral-spiritual aspects of readiness for military service. The main worldview ideas of military-patriotic education are universal and humanistic values that draw the individual's attention to the principles of democracy and humanism during its formation and development. In particular, the criteria for the effectiveness of military-patriotic education are the level of patriotic readiness of students, as well as indicators in various areas, such as education, physical fitness, psychological stability, social interaction and moral-spiritual readiness for military service. In this way, it is possible to single out and systematize the components of effective implementation of patriotic education (Table 1).

Table 1.

Components of Effective Implementation of National-Patriotic Education

Destruction of Anti-Ukrainian Stereotypes and Narratives	Cultivating a Polite and Tactful Attitude Towards Oneself and Others	Age Category Consideration	Paying Attention to Regional Features
Combined Collective and Individual Approach	National-Patriotic Education		Careful Information Base Development
Clarifying the Concepts of Sustainable Development and Healthy Lifestyle	Drawing Attention on the Identity and Independence of the Ukrainian People	Getting Acquainted with Heroic Periods in the Ukrainian History	Selection of the Most Prominent Historical Figures

Source: *Materials of Study Conducted.*

It is this comprehensive approach that can create interest and respect among young people for a patriotic way of life.

Since Ukraine regained its independence, there has been a change in the official position of the government in the eastern and southern regions of the country, but the implementation of patriotic education initiatives through hasty bureaucratic measures, often without taking into account the preferences of the local population, has become an important factor in the growth of social stratification. To solve this problem, on April 3, 2006,

there was formed a working group on patriotic education of youth in terms of the National Security and Defence Council. The goal of the group was to promote the development of a national concept of patriotic education of youth. The group included leading experts from various governmental bodies of Ukraine, including the Ministry of Youth and the Ministry of Education, as well as representatives of NGOs, youth organizations, creative intellectuals and recognized scientists. Moreover, the group collaborated with a wide group of national theorists and practitioners who specialize in

youth education. This joint work aimed to ensure an inclusive approach and respond to the diverse needs and views of Ukrainian youth. [25, 28.03.2019].

The next stage in the development of the Institute of Patriotic Education in Ukraine was the adoption on March 26, 2015 of the Concept of National Patriotic Education of Children and Youth for the period 2015–2019 by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, which provided for several stages of the implementation of relevant initiatives. At the first stage (2015), attention should be paid to the establishment of legal support and the creation of an informational and methodological base for national and patriotic education. Moreover, there was foreseen the creation of a Center for Patriotic Education and an information resource on national and patriotic issues. The second stage (2016–2017) provided for the development of curriculums and materials for various levels of education, as well as scientific and methodological manuals to support the training and work of clubs and centers engaged in patriotic education. The last stage (2018–2019) provided for the monitoring of the patriotic education system through sociological studies and scientific and methodological conferences, as well as the adjustment of pedagogical approaches based on the obtained results [25, 28.03.2019].

In 2015–2021, there were also approved the “Strategy of National Patriotic Education for 2016–2020” (Decree of the President of Ukraine dated October 13, 2015 No. 580/20152015), the “Concept of National Patriotic Education in the Education System of Ukraine” (Decree of the Ministry of Education and Culture of Ukraine No. 1038 dated July 29, 2019), the document “On the Strategy of National Patriotic Education” (Decree of the President of Ukraine dated May 21, 2019 No. 286/2019). At the same time, in 2021, there was adopted the Military Security Strategy of Ukraine [22], approved by the Decree of the President of Ukraine No. 121 dated March 25, 2021 [11], which also discussed the development of national and patriotic education. In parallel with these measures, civic initiatives appeared, such as the proposal of the Institute of Human Self-Development “Samriti” to introduce the textbook “Course of a Young Patriot” into the educational process, which takes into account psychological and emotional aspects in education.

In order to effectively integrate the military-patriotic education of the young generation into the education system, the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine has the opportunity to perform a number of tasks in the short- and long-term perspective. These tasks include the development of a military-patriotic education methodology for use by educators, conducting empirical research to develop an innovative approach to the formation of certain moral qualities in the young generation. The development of pupils' competences in the field of safety is also determined to be important. To achieve the set goals, the academy plans to substantiate the scientific-theoretical and methodical principles of military-patriotic education of high school pupils, taking into account the actual experience of national resistance. In addition, it is planned to conduct monitoring studies to determine the level of formation

of defence consciousness among educators and their achievements in the field of security [2]. It is also worth noting that in a number of laws and regulations, such as the laws of Ukraine “On the Basic Principles of State Policy in the Field of Building Ukrainian National and Civil Identity” (2022) [19]. “Law of Ukraine “On the basic principles of state policy in the sphere of establishing Ukrainian national and civil identity” dated 13. 12.2022 No. 2834-IX) and “On the Fundamentals of National Resistance” (2021) [20], as well as in the concepts and programs focused on the organization of national resistance in order to counteract the full-scale aggression of the Russian Federation, there was determined the need of increasing the defence potential of the state. These documents also emphasize the cohesion of society, the military-patriotic education of citizens, as well as the readiness of the population to defend the state under the conditions of the armed aggression of the Russian Federation against Ukraine. Also, on February 14, 2022, the Day of Unity was introduced to strengthen the consolidation of Ukrainian society and increase its resistance to hybrid threats, information propaganda, as well as moral and psychological pressure on public consciousness. Holding the Day of Unity is the duty of state institutions, which, in accordance with the Law of Ukraine “On Urgent Measures for the Consolidation of Ukrainian Society”, shall raise the State Flag of Ukraine on buildings and structures in all populated areas on February 16 of each year. There was provided for the performance of the National Anthem of Ukraine at 10:00 a.m. It is also provided for the organization of appropriate measures aimed at strengthening unity and support of Ukraine in diplomatic missions of Ukraine abroad [12].

The formation of civil society, strengthening of historical and cultural awareness of citizens, as well as the formation of a patriotic worldview therein can be identified as separate aspects of national-patriotic education. A developed civil society is important for the functioning of the state, especially a democratic one, and therefore in modern political science there are two theories of the essence of civil society. The first theory considers civil society as a social universality, which is a set of social relations opposed to the state in any of its forms. The second theory defines civil society as a certain phenomenon, which is an effective form of existence of a democratic society related to the formation of a citizen with his/her own freedoms, rights and duties. In the modern definition of civil society, the most widespread is the idea thereof as a system of social associations and relations between individuals separated from the state. This system creates conditions for self-realization of individuals and collectives in various areas of society, uniting activists with high moral qualities. In turn, understanding the history, values, symbols and identity of the Ukrainian people requires the development of modern Ukrainian cultural studies. It is important that cultural studies got sufficient support and encouragement from the state, and access to modern literature, research tools and databases that contribute to the development of cultural studies in Ukraine should always be open to education applicants and research fellows. The formation of a patriotic worldview in the

younger generation is also crucial for ensuring the stability of state institutions during the war, which is achieved due to effective patriotic education combined with preservation of the traditions and culture of the people.

We conducted a survey regarding paying due attention to national-patriotic education by the state in Ukraine as a whole and in educational institutions in particular. Its results are given in the table (Table 2).

Table 2.

Interview on Patriotic Education

Question	Yes	No	It is Difficult to Answer
How do you think enough attention to patriotic education in Ukraine is paid by the state?	52%	11,5%	36,5%
How do you think more attention should be paid to patriotic education in Ukraine?	74,3%	5,7%	20%
How do you think patriotic education should be given more attention in educational institutions?	78,4%	14,2%	7,4%

Source: *Materials of Survey Conducted.*

Thus, the conducted interview points out that, according to the majority of interviewed citizens, more attention should be paid to patriotic education than it is currently. At the same time, most of the respondents do not see the fault of the state as a whole in this, but only of certain of its social institutions, which are educational institutions.

However, not only youth representatives need patriotic education, but also civil servants, in particular in the bodies of the security and defence sector of Ukraine. It is necessary to focus attention on improving the quality of personnel support at all stages: from the selection of personnel to their study, professional training and retraining. Special attention should be paid to

aspects of motivation, compliance with professional requirements, patriotic education of employees and improvement of their practical skills [12] (Reznikova O. O., 2022). Such a position once again confirms not only the very existence, but also the importance of the security aspect of patriotic education. Another confirmation of this is statistical data, which should also be considered as the result of active patriotic education. Thus, according to experts of O. Razumkov Ukrainian Center for Economic and Political Studies, in sociological studies, readiness to defend the state is one of the greatest indicators of patriotism. The Center also provides the results of sociological surveys on other indicators and issues (Table 3).

Table 3.

Comparative Table of Sociological Surveys

Answer to a Question or Position	2011	2020	2022	Dynamics (% per year)
Willingness to defend our country	40%	57%	71%	from +1,88% to +7%
What is more important - freedom or equality? (freedom was chosen)	–	64%	71%	+3,5%
What is more important - freedom or security? (safety was chosen)	–	66%	56%	-5%

Source: *statistical data from the article of the National Security and Defence Magazine* [44, p. 13].

With the beginning of the Russian full-scale invasion in February 2022, the trend in the readiness of Ukrainians to defend the Fatherland changed. If in 2011, 40% of Ukrainians answered affirmatively to the question of readiness to defend the country, in 2020 – 57%, and according to the sociological survey conducted by the Razumkov Center from May 23 to 31, 2023 – 67%. In particular, the majority of the population of all its regions are ready to defend Ukraine: 61% - in the East, 67% - in the Central regions, 68% - in the Western regions and 71% - in the South of the country. Among them, 74% are men, 60.5% are women. Regarding age, from 18 to 59 years old - from 68% to 75%, 60 years and older – 51% [46].

The survey covered 2,020 people aged 18 and

over. The theoretical sampling error does not exceed 2.3%. At the same time, additional sample deviations are possible due to the consequences of Russian aggression, in particular the forced evacuation of millions of civilians. It was conducted by the method of stratified multistage sampling with random sampling at the first stage of sample formation and quota selection of respondents at the last stage. Respondents were selected by gender and age quotas in accordance with the demographic composition of the adult population of the studied regions at the beginning of 2022 [46].

Thus, the following trends can be distinguished: the readiness to defend Ukraine has increased rapidly due to a full-scale invasion, freedom is gradually becoming the greatest value for citizens, since it was the

Russian Federation that encroached on it by starting armed aggression.

Modern national interests of Ukraine and strategic goals in the formation of a new political system of the nation pose special tasks to educators in the field of national-patriotic education. Patriotism, as an important component of sociocultural identity, is expressed in devotion to the state and people, readiness to protect their interests from external and internal threats. Effective national-patriotic education involves the development of civic-patriotic, military-patriotic and spiritual-moral components. Such education is one of the important areas of the state policy in young generation education, aimed at the formation of national consciousness based on the values and ideals of the Ukrainian nation. Thus, the modern national interests of Ukraine and strategic goals in the formation of a new political system of the nation place a special emphasis on the national-patriotic education of pupils. Once again, attention is drawn to the fact that national-patriotic education involves the development of the main components: civil, military and spiritual. However, it is worth emphasizing that such education becomes effective only when these components are skillfully combined. That is why patriotic education is one of the priorities of state and public policy, focused on the formation of national consciousness, patriotic personality of a citizen and promoting the education of the young generation based on the values and ideals of the Ukrainian nation.

The volunteer movement is an important factor in the unity of ukrainian society

The consolidation of Ukrainian society is manifested in the common goals, interests and actions of all citizens, in particular in the establishment of partnership relations between the main social groups, social support of the population by the authorities, active participation of citizens in the interests of the city, region, and country as a whole organism. Unity itself is an important factor that helped Ukraine resist and restrain the enemy when it tried to break into the approaches of the capital, and today it helps step by step to de-occupy Ukrainian territories in the South and East of the country.

One of the important factors of the unity of Ukrainians and the formation of national and patriotic feelings among young people is their volunteering. Volunteering for schoolchildren is an inexhaustible source of energy for acquiring civic education, learning and contributing to the development of the consolidation of Ukrainian society, an opportunity to realize oneself in service to the same. During the difficult time of war for Ukraine, volunteers help our soldiers as much as they can. In particular, they participate in the production of camouflage nets, online challenges "Together to Victory", write letters to the defenders, expressing their moral support, supply them with medicine, food, personal hygiene products etc. For this purpose, charity fairs and other actions are held in schools, the collected funds are transferred to the purchase of everything necessary for the Armed Forces of Ukraine. As an example, at the end of February 2024, pupils of Bucha Community in Kyiv Region held a charity fair for two days to support the Ukrainian military. Thanks to the sale of

goodies, seven schools of this community collected UAH 436,820 for the Armed Forces of Ukraine. Pupils of Bucha Gymnasium No. 2 and Lyceum No. 9 also raised funds for kamikaze drones for military purposes. The drones were handed over to the fighters of the 63rd separate mechanized brigade in Lyman direction [34].

In Kropyvnytskyi there is an alternative school "KrOK", whose pupils know what volunteering is not from books or social networks. They regularly visit the local animal protection organizations "BIM" and "Happy Dog", have repeatedly volunteered at the locations of running marathons, organize charity events and flea markets, safety workshops. Starting the second day of the full-scale invasion, they began weaving camouflage nets for the AFU here. Both children and parents gathered in the sports hall.

Almost from the first days of the war, Bar schools (Vinnytsia Region) also joined volunteer activities. Someone prepared food for the military and displaced persons, somewhere there was a warehouse for food and humanitarian aid, and somewhere there was an overnight reception point for displaced persons traveling in transit. From the beginning of the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation into the territory of Ukraine, the kitchen of the Bar Lyceum No.2 became a place for preparing various dishes for Ukrainian defenders and immigrants. Local volunteers accepted products for the formation of consignments for the AFU in the premises of the educational institution, and at the beginning of the war the local authorities accepted humanitarian consignments from sister cities, etc.

Good deeds, which start from school years, educate children to understand the feelings and needs of others, the ability to accumulate experience of social interaction and communication. Young people should engage in charity, as it helps them to see different aspects of good, allows them to accumulate experience of social interaction and communication, and forms value and moral guidelines in schoolchildren.

Due to social activities, young volunteers acquire practical life goals, experience, master the art of life creation, self-development of personality.

The traditional curriculum is mainly focused on the passive consumption of a large amount of information. Instead, through volunteering, an active position of the child is formed, who becomes a participant in the processes, nurtures a sense of responsibility for what is happening. Volunteerism forms a conscious society in which most citizens are successful. Today, the actions of Ukrainian volunteers and ordinary people led to a rethinking of charity in the world, and the volunteer movement plays one of the key roles in this terrible war.

Thus, national-patriotic education is an activity of the state and activists, aimed at the development and spread of patriotism among the population of the state, in particular, the youth, to support identity and historical & cultural independence, preservation of national memory, as well as the development of patriots as healthy, cultural and educated individuals who are morally and physically capable of defending the state if needed. The main principles of national-patriotic edu-

cation should include: state-wide obligatory implementation, personal voluntariness of involvement, highlighting of historical truth, cultural and physical development of a patriot. The main aspects of national-patriotic education are: social, educational, protective and cultural. The social aspect of patriotic education is determined by the possibility of qualitative identification of an individual in society as a patriot through the individual's active part in such education or its implementation or organization. The communicative aspect is manifested in the positive influence of this activity on the formation of personality from the point of view of the basic principles of proper behaviour of a well-educated person and the basic skills of polite social communication. The protective aspect is directly related to the relevant readiness of the patriot, which includes both physical and moral components, to protect Ukraine. The cultural aspect is expressed in the cultural and educational influence of patriotic education, which is carried out by introducing students to important historical figures of the Ukrainian national and cultural revival, heroic pages from the history of Ukraine and outstanding works of Ukrainian classical literature.

The need to develop a system of national-patriotic education is caused by the following factors: patriotic education can unite society and direct its efforts to the defence of Ukraine; such education is a qualitative response to the propaganda of the Russian Federation; while nurturing national identity, patriotic education is designed to promote the protection of Ukrainian history, culture and traditions.

Within modern Russian aggression, the system of national-patriotic education needs revision, improvement and strengthening. Among the main measures: improvement of the regulatory and legal framework regarding national-patriotic education; participation in national-patriotic education of local authorities and local self-government; creation of interschool resource centers, socio-pedagogical conditions for the implementation of national-patriotic education; modification of the content and forms of national-patriotic education; organization of information and educational work in the field of national-patriotic education etc. [3, p. 24].

We also consider it necessary to express certain proposals and recommendations regarding its improvement and development of national-patriotic education. **First**, patriotic education should become obligatory at all levels of education, have specific, standardized programs approved by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, and should be provided with the necessary number of hours, which, according to the resolution of the expert commission of the ministry, will be sufficient for the effective conduct of patriotic education in each age category of schoolchildren, cadets and students. **Second**, patriotic education should be implemented not only through educational institutions, but also through national mass media, patriotic communities and centers, social media in order to achieve the maximum coverage of the audience, since patriotic education should be carried out for all citizens of Ukraine. **Third**, patriotic education should receive proper support from the state book publishing house, which should not only print and sell patriotic literature, but

also act as the initiator of its creation.

Discussions

As it was found out, the main aspects of national-patriotic education in Ukraine are paying maximum attention to the Ukrainian language, culture, history and the citizen's duty to protect the state.

According to A. Giudici and S. Grizelj, at the end of the XIX century, the relationship between the state, language and education became extremely complicated: the state hoped that education would reflect national identity, while the true nation was seen as monolingual. According to the literature on national identity, education was responsible for the formation of such an identity, and therefore curriculums usually promoted the use of a single language. This theory, which developed mainly in the context of monolingual national states, does not coincide with the position of democratic multilingual states [16]. However, it should be noted that although this new perspective affected all curriculums in different ways, it can be agreed that economic and pedagogical considerations were also important factors in the formation of language curriculums, along with national identity.

The importance of raising the level of ideological and political education to ensure not only professional but also patriotic education is exceptional. The result of such combined training should be educated talented citizens who possess not only professional skills, but also ethical values and a wider vision of the world [42]. This way, they will be able to better navigate in our time of unprecedented changes and more effectively contribute to the unity of Ukrainian society.

Textbooks from different historical periods, including modern ones are of particular importance for the formation of historical worldview of citizens and their ability to compare past events with the present [17].

Museums play an important role in the preservation and popularization of history, culture and social heritage. They are important centers where the material and spiritual values of the country are preserved and demonstrated, contributing to the formation of cultural self-awareness and patriotism among citizens [32].

When forming concepts for the introduction of patriotic education in Ukraine, geographical distance from the cultural centers of individual regions of the state should also be taken into account. We agree that a balanced approach to patriotic education and an understanding of the concept of patriotism is one that should be implemented by any state, which was also indirectly mentioned in the conducted study.

National-patriotic education plays a significant role in both general secondary and higher education, helping students to understand national culture and strengthen feelings of love and pride for their country. In secondary education, teachers actively work to inculcate patriotic values among students through classroom activities, using textbook materials, other valuable resources such as historical artifacts, cultural heritage and the achievements of outstanding scientists. The introduction of additional getting acquainted with the main life milestones and achievements of prominent

Ukrainian figures into school programs has the potential to enrich the educational process, helping teachers to create exciting educational activities and classes that are necessary not only for patriotic education, but also for effective and interesting learning. Agreeing with the idea of using national heritage items, it should be clarified that such artefacts should be placed in appropriate national museums, which should be given free access, especially to the younger generation.

According to V. Nedzinskaitė-Mitkė and N. Stasiulis, citizens within modern national states often face certain questions in terms of loyalty to their nation and state. Every self-conscious citizen tries to find a delicate balance between patriotic feelings and economic interests, individual rights and national well-being, as well as material needs and abstract ideals. It is in these searches that patriotic education should become a support [24.]. Unfortunately, it is impossible to agree with the position when a citizen opposes economic interests to patriotism, as this is one of the manifestations of insufficient patriotic upbringing. However, it should be noted that the timely establishment of an unfavourable development of the social situation in this area makes it possible to promptly regulate it.

Children's patriotic books, which are available in bookstores and can often be seen in various home and educational environments, also play an important role in patriotic education. Against the background of a social and political context where patriotism has historically been used by powerful elites to justify their actions and positions, as well as where approaches to teaching patriotism in schools are currently being actively debated, such books can be used against the people. While many authors seek to support a modern and inclusive form of patriotism, they also unwittingly support certain social attitudes that form hierarchical ideas about who and in what capacity has the right to membership in the national community [21]. The issue of proper literary support for patriotic education is always painful, since the young generation should see a positive example of a patriotic citizen in books or textbooks, and not face stereotypes and imposed ideas of dividing society into those and others. On the other side, developed patriotic education on the part of the state can neutralize such negative manifestations, in particular, if the state actively publishes state patriotic literature, which was already emphasized in this article.

In modern discussions about patriotic education, various views reveal differences between supporters of universalism and cosmopolitanism on the one side and supporters of communitarianism on the other one [18]. And although patriotism is not a legal obligation, the moral aspect of this phenomenon stems from the need for self-awareness of self-national identity by a citizen. However, it should be noted that the state shall solely define the concept and content of patriotism and patriotic education, since such ambiguity in the circle of scientists can develop into doubts about other issues in this area, discrediting the state position.

Today, patriotism does play an important role, especially in the context of the unity of a democratic society that functions as a joint enterprise, where members of the community are bound by laws and rules that

govern their behaviour and interactions. This is important for ensuring the coordination of public actions and solving collective problems. Patriotism also encourages citizens to actively participate in democratic processes, to prioritize the common good over personal interests. It promotes the development of a sense of civic responsibility and public spirit, which are important components for the effective functioning of a democracy [9.]. Therefore, the support of patriotic instructions and values in democratic education is considered important, as it contributes to the formation of active and responsible citizens who are able to participate in the common cause of society development. It should be agreed that in a democratic society patriotism is of great importance, as it unites society with the common goal of ensuring the effective functioning of the state and its development.

National-patriotic education, which is deeply rooted in general education, really contributes to the formation of national consciousness and promotes patriotic ideals. In particular, it is worth paying attention to certain methods and approaches. The use of various educational channels, which consists in the inclusion of patriotic materials in the curriculums of various subjects, the use of multimedia resources and interactive platforms to increase the accessibility and interest of the educational material. Heuristic teaching methods, in turn, promote the active participation of students in their own learning, allow them to solely discover and analyze historical facts and events. It is also important to emphasize the importance of historical truthfulness, in order to ensure the reflection of an objective picture of history and culture of the country in educational materials, and not their distorted or one-sided version. Much attention is also paid to the use of innovative educational tools and technologies in education, the creation of open distance courses, virtual tours and interactive programs to engage students in the study of history and culture of the country [14.]. (Gao C., Jiang, Q., Shi, Y., Jiang, W., Xie X., 2023). Instead, modern youth requires innovative approaches to patriotic education, because they are more getting acquainted with the achievements of scientific and technical progress, and master them more skillfully and quickly. However, we note that the implementation of such initiatives is not always possible on the part of educational institutions, in particular due to a lack of appropriate training or technical support.

Having analyzed the positions, arguments and historical experience of domestic and foreign scientists in relation to patriotic education, we can state that the main aspects of such education coincide in most cases with small regional and national features, which include paying attention to national sports and martial arts, national musical instruments, emphasizing the important role of pre-school and school patriotic education, the involvement of innovative and technological approaches in learning and patriotic education of young people.

Conclusions

In this way, there were conducted the studies of national-patriotic education in the conditions of genocidal war, as a factor of the unity of Ukrainian society.

There were considered the concepts of patriotism and patriotic education, the process of its development, formation and current state, as well as there was substantiated the need for the formation of a patriotic outlook among citizens. The results of the study show that national-patriotic education is an effective tool of the state and the public to support identity and historical-cultural independence, preserve national memory and develop patriots ready to defend Ukraine. The principles of national-patriotic education, such as state-wide obligatory implementation, personal voluntary participation, highlighting of historical truth, cultural and physical development of a patriot, emphasize the importance of this process in the formation of civic consciousness and the unity of Ukrainian society. There were also highlighted the social, communicative, protective and cultural aspects of national-patriotic education. The social aspect contributes to the qualitative identification of an individual in society as a patriot through active participation in patriotic education and the organization of such measures. The communicative aspect has a positive effect on personality development by forming the basic principles of polite behaviour and respectful social communication skills. The protective aspect of national-patriotic education emphasizes the importance of a patriot's physical and moral readiness to defend the state during a threat. The cultural aspect is manifested in the cultural and educational influence of patriotic education through getting acquainted with historical events and prominent figures of the Ukrainian national and cultural revival. Certain recommendations were also presented regarding the effective further development of the social institution of the state.

The phenomenon of Ukrainian donations became the main factor that significantly paid the attention of the world public to charity. Foreigners still do not understand how in a country where there is a war, people themselves collect millions of UAH in a short period of time for attack and naval drones, satellites, military vehicles and equipment, ammunition and other weapons.

In addition, the number of people engaged in volunteering in Ukraine is probably much larger than in any other country in the world. Ukrainian volunteers solve all kinds of issues at any time.

Thus, Ukrainian volunteers and ordinary Ukrainians became a reliable rear of the soldiers of the Armed Forces of Ukraine. And this unity, which surprised the world in the first days of the Russian invasion, unites society in the future, becoming a driving force for good deeds.

Summing up, we note that the formation of national-patriotic consciousness in the conditions of a genocidal war is a key factor in the unity of the Ukrainian people, contributes to the strengthening of the socio-economic, spiritual, cultural foundations of the development of Ukrainian society and the state, the maintenance of national identity and independence, helping Ukrainians not to forget their roots and the true history of Ukraine. Further development of the concepts of principles, aspects, necessary conditions for the effectiveness of patriotic education in Ukraine should be included among the areas of possible studies.

In the conducted studies, the issues of the methodological basis of such education and the main pedagogical techniques for its implementation in practice were not considered in detail, which can also serve as topics for separate studies.

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